

Gallery Walk Learning Model on Writing Exposition Texts

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ABSTRACT

This study (1) examines how the Gallery Walk methodology helps class X students at SMA Negeri 1 Makassar write explanatory texts. (2) to evaluate the gallery walk model's effects on class X SMA Negeri 1 Makassar students' exposition writing activities and learning outcomes. The study is quasi-experimental. The study population is SMA Negeri 1 Makassar class X pupils. Study sample This sampled intentionally The designation is 52 person student. The experiment class has 34 students and the control class has 18. Research instruments These include interview instructions, sample observation sheets, student learning exercises, and tests. The Lilliefors test, Levene test, and independent sample t-test were employed to test data normality, homogeneity, and hypothesis. Hypothesis testing for student learning effectiveness yielded t counts $>$ t tables ($7.505 > 2.012$) and significance $0.000 < 0.05$, while student learning outcomes yielded t counts $>$ t tables ($6.699 > 2.012$) and significance $0.000 < 0.05$. Data shows that the gallery walk model improves writing exposition texts in class X pupils at SMA Negeri 1 Makassar better than the conventional model.

INTRODUCTION

Education is vital to humanity. To live, everyone requires a focused education. Quality education affects national progress because it helps people attain their greatest potential. According to Aunurrahman (2014: 5), "education must have a balance in its role build student as inhabitant world, nation and public the good one". Munib et al. (2012: 27) state that "education has the task of producing good human beings, more cultured human beings, humans as individuals who have more personality Good".

This notion of education suggests that everyone needs it. To live and develop all my potential as a student. Chapter II Article 3 of Constitution Number 20 of 2003 states: "National education functions to develop the potential of students to become human beings who believe, fear God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, and become citizens who democratic and responsible answer". If every level and educational unit applies a quality learning method to maximize students' potential, national education can be achieved. According to Setijowati (2013: 2), "Learning is an effort to guide students so that students are consciously willing to carry out learning activities". Teachers and students engage in learning activities. Teachers as learning designers must consider student traits.

Teachers must focus on all aspects of learning, including student development. Teachers directly engage students as subjects and learning objects. No matter how good the degree program, training, or infrastructure are. Not everything is matched with teacher quality in teaching. Teacher skill is crucial to learning, especially in basic education. Basic education is the cornerstone of student growth. Indonesian language instruction is crucial for pupils. This topic is provided to high school (SMA) students since they are required to understand, grasp, and use language abilities. Like reading, hearing, writing, and speaking. According to content standards by the National Education Unit Agency (2006) in Sufanti (2012: 11), learning Indonesian aims to improve students' oral and written communication skills and foster appreciation of Indonesian literature. The objectives of studying Indonesian are to improve written and spoken communication on official and unofficial situations. Language skills are needed for socialization.

Indonesian high school (SMA) students must compose explanatory literature. Wrong, says Tarmizi (2013: 12). Writing, one of four language abilities (listening, speaking, reading, and writing), involves communicating ideas clearly to others. Writing allows a person to express their thoughts, intentions, and messages to others, according to Abidin (2014: 19). Writing is a way to express thoughts and share them to others. The Indonesian language teaching model is entertaining and should improve students' comprehension. Thus, the learning model is crucial to objective learning. Teachers employ standard learning paradigms rather than new ones. The traditional model emphasizes teachers, reading, and homework. Interviews with high school Indonesian language teachers found that novel learning techniques, such as the Gallery Walk model, had never been used.

Most Indonesian language learning gallery materials emphasize student understanding, particularly exposition text writing. The Indonesian language course explains to pupils the goals of learning Indonesian and how to communicate in formal and informal contexts using various media. Orally and in writing. The process of socialization involves language skills. Basic and advanced writing lessons exist. We learn to write overnight and through practice. Objective literacy requires distinct strategies, methods, and models from teachers. Wrong One method For aid Focusing on model learning will help you achieve your learning goals. The Gallery Walk paradigm can be used to generate exposition materials. Silberman (2014: 274) states that "Model Gallery Walk helps students recall what they've learned by constructing a list of words and assessing them together. The Gallery Walk methodology engages students in learning since they can correct each other if they discover something new student.

The Gallery Walk Learning Model aids students in understanding learning ideas. This learning approach enables students to work together in small groups to share pre-existing information with other groups, enabling opportunities for inquiry, discussion, and self-expression. Students will participate in discussions, provide feedback to one other, and deliver presentations to actively participate in classroom education. Each group presents their work, the teacher provides clarification, and then ends to avoid any confusion. Gallery Walk learning is both enjoyable and engages students both physically and mentally. The benefits of the Gallery Walk learning approach make it suitable for creating exposition texts.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Indonesian high school (SMA) students must compose explanatory literature. Wrong, says Tarmizi (2013: 12). Writing, one of four language abilities (listening, speaking, reading, and writing), involves communicating ideas clearly to others. Writing allows a person to express their thoughts, intentions, and messages to others, according to Abidin (2014: 19). Writing is a way to express thoughts and share them to others. The Indonesian language teaching model is entertaining and should improve students' comprehension. Thus, the learning model is crucial to objective learning. Teachers employ standard learning paradigms rather than new ones. The traditional model emphasizes teachers, reading, and homework.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study is empirical. Experimental research involves conducting controlled investigations to investigate variations in treatments. This study employs a quantitative descriptive methodology. Quantitative research studies populations or samples, gathers numerical data, and analyzes it to assess theories. Researchers at SMA Negeri 1 Makassar analyzed the exposition text writing of class X students following the implementation of the Gallery Walk learning paradigm.

This study utilized an experimental design. This experiment tries to acquire knowledge that is at least equivalent to that obtained from information that does not control learning processes. Experimental research employs the nonequivalent pretest-posttest group design. Design-oriented, The selection of the experimental and control groups must be prioritized. Subsequently, administer identical pretest and posttest questions to both the control group and the experimental class. Two models were employed for teaching exposition writing: the control class utilized the traditional approach, while the experimental class employed the gallery tour model. Silbermen (2014: 247)'s Gallery Walk model involves: a) Grouping students; b) Instructing them to recall or discover new knowledge related to the theme; c) Listing words learned; d) Selecting and writing appropriate words into poetry sentences; e) Displaying the completed work.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two classes were studied: an experimental class that learned using the gallery walk model and a control class that used the standard model. SMA Negeri 1 Makassar conducted 2021/2022 academic year research in January 2022. It included 52 students: 34 in class X1 (experimental) and 18 in class X2 (control). Activity learning during eight 16-hour classes on class experiment or control. Second class is treated as pretest and posttest.

The pretest assesses students' exposition writing skills before receiving the information. Different learning exercises are given to each class. The experimental class used the gallery walk model, while the control class used the standard model. A posttest was given at the end of the study to compare learning outcomes between the two classes after learning the same content using different learning models. It also compares the gallery walk paradigm to conventional models for efficacy. Research data description and analysis are presented below.

To simplify study outcomes, data description describes the distribution of research data. The gallery walk learning model variable data, experimental and control class posttest results, activity variables, and student learning outcomes are described here. This study applied the gallery walk learning model to exposition text writing. At the first meeting, the gallery walk learning model for students was seen and scored 87.5% with extremely high criteria. At the second meeting, the final score was 92% with high standards. Two learning meetings yielded gallery walk learning model observation scores.

Table 1. Summary of Observation Value of the Gallery Walk Model for Students

Meeting	Observed Aspects	Score (%)	Criteria
1		87.5	Very high
2		92	Very high

- Students prepare themselves to receive lesson.
- Students pay attention to the teacher's explanation during delivery material.
- Students ask questions with Teacher.
- Students follow the learning steps with Good.
- Students work on questions evaluation.
- Students complete learning in an orderly manner calm.

Observational data recapitulation of the gallery walk learning model for students shows that the experimental class already applies certain components. The model observation score covers tall criteria. Once the activity data and Indonesian learning results on the exposition text writing material are normally distributed and homogeneous, test the final hypothesis. Final hypothesis testing using SPSS Version 22's independent-sample t-test. Under the assumption that this study's data are ratios and independent comparative hypotheses (2 samples), this technique is applied. Menu: analyze-compare means-independent-sample t-test.

Test the Effectiveness of Class X Students' Learning Activities at SMA Negeri 1 Makassar

Use the SPSS 22 independent sample t test to evaluate the Gallery Walk learning model on student learning activities and outcomes. This test determines treatment efficacy in experimental and control groups. The researcher utilized SPSS 22 for this exam. Table 4.2 shows the independent sample t test findings for the gallery tour model's effectiveness for student learning.

Table 2. Independent Sample T Test Learning Activity Test Results Student

Independent Samples Test									
	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances			t-test for Equality of Means					
	F	Sig.	Q	Df	Sig. (2tailed)	Means difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
Equal variances assumed	.702	.406	7,505	48	.000	9,873	1.316	7,228	12,518
Equal variances not assumed			7,843	32,972	.000	9,873	1,259	7,312	12,434

Table above suggests marking column sig.(2-tailed) as 0.000. The significance level is $0.000 < 0.05$. The study sample was 52 participants, hence $dk = n - 2 = 50 - 2 = 48$ and 5% error rate. The 2-sided test ($0.05: 2 = 2.5\%$) yields $t_{table} = 2.012$. The Equal variances assumed column has $t_{count} = 7.505$. Results: $7.505 > 2.012$ ($t_{count} > t_{table}$) with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. The test results show that experimental class pupils learn Indonesian better than the control class. Thus, the gallery walk learning technique is highly efficient in Indonesian language classes on exposition text writing. The class that uses model galleries walks taller, according to research on student learning outcomes. Thus, the gallery walk approach improves writing exposition texts in class X SMA Negeri 1 Makassar compared to the conventional model.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The research and discussion results indicate that using the Gallery Walk learning model is effective for enhancing the activity and outcomes of writing expository texts in Class X at SMA Negeri 1 Makassar. This can be demonstrated by the study's student score average of 82.02, which falls into the extremely high range. The average score on the study results is 85.85. The study revealed variations in the Indonesian language learning activities of class X students in exposition text writing material when comparing those utilizing the gallery walk model and those using standard learning models. The results of hypothesis testing were calculated using the independent sample t test in the SPSS version 22 program, indicating that the gallery tour model has a substantial impact on student learning activities. The impact of the gallery walk model on student learning activities is significant, with a t-value of 7.505 being greater than 2.012, indicating statistical significance. The significance level is less than 0.05, namely 0.000. Furthermore Utilize an independent samples t-test to evaluate the hypothesis. Test results showed that using model galleries during the eye instruction was successful for the X class students in the study. An expository text in Indonesian language was written to study the effectiveness of gallery walk models on student outcomes. The study found that the average marks in the experimental class were higher than those in the control class. The experimental class had an average mark of 85.85, while the control class had an average of 73.37. Furthermore, the statistical tests showed that the acquired t count value was 6.699, which is greater than the t table value of 2.012. Additionally, the significance value was 0.000, indicating statistical significance since it is less than 0.05.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research on the topic still needs to be carried out "Gallery Walk Learning Model on Writing Exposition Texts."

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Dewi, Pannaco, Risnah, Matande, Indrawati

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